

Examining Socio-Cultural and Institutional Constraints to Women's Involvement in National Agricultural Governance in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examines socio-cultural and institutional constraints on women's involvement in national agricultural governance in Nigeria, with a focus on the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) of Abuja. Using a mixed-methods approach, data were collected from 275 respondents—female farmers, policymakers, and representatives of women's agricultural organisations such as WOFAN and NWAPDI — through structured questionnaires, focus group discussions, and in-depth interviews. The study found that women's participation in agricultural decision-making is growing, with 74.5% of respondents actively involved in policy discussions and governance processes. Awareness of federal agricultural ministries and gender-inclusive programs was relatively high, yet socio-cultural norms, limited access to resources, and underrepresentation in leadership roles remain significant barriers. Although policies such as the National Gender Policy and National Agricultural Transformation Implementation Policy (NATIP) have promoted inclusion, their inconsistent implementation limits women's effective participation. Findings indicate that while women contribute meaningfully to agricultural governance, systemic reforms, targeted capacity-building, and cultural reorientation are necessary to achieve full gender equity. The study recommends strengthening institutional mechanisms, enhancing policy dissemination, and promoting community-level advocacy to support women's leadership in agriculture. Overall, integrating women's perspectives into decision-making is essential for equitable governance, sustainable agricultural development, and improved food security in Nigeria.

Keywords: Women Empowerment, Agricultural Governance, Gender Inclusion, Socio-Cultural Constraints, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture remains a cornerstone of Nigeria's economy, employing over 35% of the nation's labour force and contributing significantly to its Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2023). Despite this centrality, women, who constitute nearly half of the agricultural workforce, remain underrepresented in governance and decision-making within the sector (Food and Agriculture Organisation [FAO], 2021). Women play vital roles in food production, processing, and marketing (Muhammed et al., 2025). However, their voices are often excluded from policy formulation, institutional leadership, and national agricultural planning (Ogunlela & Mukhtar, 2020). The gender gap not only undermines inclusivity but also hinders the realisation of sustainable agricultural development in Nigeria (Ahmed et al., 2024).

Socio-cultural norms are among the most pervasive barriers to women's involvement in agricultural governance (Magaji et al., 2024). In many Nigerian communities, patriarchal values define gender roles, restricting women's autonomy and limiting their access to leadership opportunities (Adekoya, 2022). These cultural practices perpetuate male dominance in decision-making structures, reinforcing the perception that women's roles are confined to domestic and subsistence farming activities (Olayemi & Adeoye, 2021). Such gendered expectations have deep historical roots and

continue to shape institutional behaviours and community attitudes toward women's participation in leadership positions within agricultural institutions.

Institutional factors further compound these socio-cultural constraints. Many agricultural agencies and cooperatives lack gender-sensitive policies that promote women's representation in governance (Aina & Yusuf, 2023). Women are often excluded from training programs (Magaji et al., 2025), policy dialogues (Musa et al., 2025), and access to resources such as land (Ibrahim & Sule), credit (Magaji & Yahaya, 2012), and technology (Abubakar et al., 2025), all of which are critical for influencing decision-making processes (FAO, 2021). Moreover, institutional bias in recruitment and promotion within agricultural ministries and organisations has limited women's progression into leadership and technical advisory roles (Ogunlela & Mukhtar, 2020). These structural inequalities reflect broader gender disparities in Nigeria's political and administrative systems.

The absence of women's voices in national agricultural governance has significant implications for policy outcomes and sectoral development. Inclusive decision-making has been shown to enhance innovation, resource efficiency, and sustainability in agricultural practices (World Bank, 2022). When women are actively involved in governance, policies are more likely to address issues of equity, productivity, and rural livelihoods holistically. Therefore, addressing the socio-cultural and institutional barriers that marginalise women is essential to achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goals 5 on gender equality and two on zero hunger.

This study examines the socio-cultural and institutional constraints that hinder women's involvement in national agricultural governance in Nigeria. By analysing both formal and informal barriers to women's participation, the research aims to inform policy reforms that foster gender inclusivity within agricultural governance structures. Understanding these challenges is vital for promoting equitable representation, empowering women in agriculture, and enhancing the effectiveness of governance in achieving sustainable agricultural transformation across Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Conceptual Review

Socio-Cultural

Socio-cultural factors refer to the values, beliefs, norms, and traditional practices that shape individual and collective behaviour within a society (Lamiya et al., 2025; Yunusa et al., 2024). In the context of gender and agriculture, socio-cultural norms often dictate gender roles and influence access to resources, power, and decision-making opportunities (Adekoya, 2022). In many parts of Nigeria, patriarchal systems reinforce male dominance in both household and community affairs, thereby limiting women's agency in leadership and governance structures (Olayemi & Adeoye, 2021). These socio-cultural dynamics perpetuate stereotypes that consider women primarily as caretakers and subsistence farmers rather than as stakeholders capable of contributing meaningfully to agricultural policy and innovation. Consequently, the persistence of these norms remains a significant barrier to women's empowerment and participation in national agricultural governance (FAO, 2021).

Institutional Constraints

Institutional constraints encompass the structural and administrative barriers within formal organisations that restrict equitable access to opportunities, resources, and decision-making roles. In Nigeria, institutional constraints manifest through gender-biased policies, inadequate representation of women in leadership positions, and limited inclusion in agricultural training and capacity-building programs (Aina & Yusuf, 2023). Many agricultural institutions lack gender-sensitive frameworks that promote inclusivity or address systemic discrimination in recruitment and promotion processes (World Bank, 2022). These constraints not only reduce women's visibility in agricultural governance but also weaken institutional performance by excluding diverse perspectives crucial for effective

policymaking. Therefore, addressing institutional barriers is essential for creating a more equitable and productive agricultural governance system in Nigeria (Ogunlela & Mukhtar, 2020).

Women's Involvement

Women's involvement refers to their active participation and representation in decision-making, policy formulation, and leadership across social, economic, and political spheres (Magaji & Aliyu, 2007). In agriculture, women's involvement encompasses resource allocation, production planning, and institutional governance (FAO, 2021). However, in Nigeria, women's participation is often constrained by gender-based discrimination (Magaji et al., 2018), limited access to credit (Musa et al., 2022), low level of literacy (Ahmad & Magaji, 2024), and socio-cultural restrictions that undermine their leadership potential (Adekoya, 2022). Enhancing women's involvement in agricultural governance not only promotes gender equity but also leads to more inclusive, effective, and sustainable policies that address the needs of all stakeholders (World Bank, 2022). Empirical studies have shown that when women are empowered to participate meaningfully, agricultural productivity, food security, and rural development outcomes improve significantly (Aina & Yusuf, 2023).

National Agricultural Governance

National agricultural governance refers to the systems, institutions, and processes through which agricultural policies are formulated, implemented, and evaluated to achieve national development goals (Ogunlela & Mukhtar, 2020). It includes the interaction of public agencies, private organisations, and community stakeholders in managing agricultural resources and ensuring sustainability. Effective agricultural governance is essential for addressing issues such as food insecurity (Magaji & Musa, 2024), climate resilience (Olusola et al., 2025), and equitable access to productive assets (World Bank, 2022). In Nigeria, challenges such as corruption (Magaji & Musa, 2015), gender inequality (Magaji & Mohammed, 2008), and weak institutional capacity often undermine governance effectiveness, leading to poor policy implementation and limited inclusivity (NBS, 2023). Promoting gender-responsive governance is therefore crucial to ensuring that agricultural development initiatives benefit both men and women equitably while advancing national sustainability objectives (FAO, 2021).

Theoretical Framework

Gender and Development (GAD) Theory

The Gender and Development (GAD) theory provides a relevant theoretical foundation for examining socio-cultural and institutional constraints to women's involvement in national agricultural governance in Nigeria. The GAD approach emerged in the 1980s as a critique of the earlier Women in Development (WID) framework, which primarily focused on integrating women into existing development structures without addressing the underlying causes of gender inequality (Moser, 1993). GAD, by contrast, emphasises the need to transform social relations and institutional practices that perpetuate gender disparities in access to power, resources, and decision-making (Rathgeber, 1990). The theory highlights that women's limited participation in agricultural governance stems not from their lack of ability, but from socio-cultural norms and institutional systems that privilege men's leadership and authority (March, Smyth, & Mukhopadhyay, 1999). Applying the GAD perspective to this study enables a critical examination of how gender relations shape agricultural policy processes and institutional structures, offering insights into strategies to promote inclusive and equitable governance in Nigeria's agricultural sector.

Empirical Review

Sallawu et al. (2022) conducted a national empirical study of 636 women farmers to identify drivers and constraints to women's participation in agricultural activities; using interviews, questionnaires, participation indices and ordered-logit regression the authors found that household size, marital status, education, farming experience, disposable income, extension contacts and association membership positively influenced participation, while distance to farm, inadequate finance and weak extension outreach remained significant constraints findings that point to both socio-cultural (household responsibilities, mobility) and institutional (credit and extension access) barriers requiring integrated policy responses.

Aimua, Adofu, and Okwori (2023) analyzed determinants of women's participation in agriculture in Lafia Metropolis using a structured questionnaire and logit regression on a sample of 210 women; the study reported that farmland size and cooperative membership were the principal determinants of active participation, whereas variables often assumed important (age, formal education, credit access, household size) were not statistically significant highlighting how institutional arrangements (land tenure and cooperative frameworks) shape women's practical inclusion in agricultural decision-making at the local level.

Shehu, Shehu, and Garba (2024) carried out a TETFUND-sponsored empirical study in Zuru Local Government (Kebbi State) combining questionnaires and primary data to assess women's contributions to food security; their results emphasised that despite women's heavy labour contributions across production, processing and marketing, socio-cultural norms, land-tenure discrimination, limited access to finance, and insecurity curtail women's agency; thus, the authors recommend gender-responsive land reforms, targeted extension services, and community-level interventions to dismantle sociocultural and institutional barriers.

Adaigho et al. (2025). (accepted Dec 2024, available online Jan 2025) used mixed methods national survey data, stakeholder interviews and policy review to examine how digital technologies and economic innovations can empower Nigerian women in agriculture; the empirical analysis showed that while ICT-enabled extension and mobile finance have potential to expand women's access to information and markets, persistent institutional exclusions (land ownership norms, lack of gender quotas in governance bodies, low digital literacy) limit benefits, leading the authors to propose an integrated policy package combining broadband expansion, gendered digital literacy, microfinance design, and institutional quotas for governance.

East-West Seed Knowledge Transfer Foundation (EWS-KT) (2025) published an evidence-based field study of 150 participants (predominantly women) in Kaduna and Kano that investigated decision-making in vegetable production; quantitative and qualitative findings showed women's high time investment and technical competence but limited decision-making power on land allocation, input choices and market relations constraints linked to household gender norms and market/institutional structures leading the report to recommend targeted input access, female-focused training, and value-chain interventions to improve women's bargaining power and representation.

Research Gap

Despite growing scholarly attention to women's participation in agriculture, the reviewed studies reveal a persistent research gap in understanding the intersection of socio-cultural and institutional barriers, specifically within *national agricultural governance structures* in Nigeria. While Sallawu et al. (2022), Aimua et al. (2023), and Shehu et al. (2024) focused primarily on women's participation at the farm or community level, they did not adequately address how structural gender biases within policymaking and administrative institutions restrict women's voices in national decision-making. Similarly, the studies by Adaigho et al. (2025) and EWS-KT (2025) explored empowerment through digital technologies and capacity building. However, they paid limited attention to institutional frameworks that shape women's access to leadership and governance platforms. Consequently, there remains a limited empirical understanding of how socio-cultural norms

interact with institutional mechanisms such as recruitment policies, representation quotas, and governance practices to perpetuate women's underrepresentation in Nigeria's agricultural policy processes. This gap underscores the need for a more comprehensive investigation into both the social and institutional dimensions that constrain women's involvement in national agricultural governance.

RESEARCH METHOD

Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which is suitable for collecting firsthand information from respondents on their perceptions and experiences regarding socio-cultural and institutional barriers affecting women's participation in agricultural governance. This design allows for the collection of quantitative and qualitative data from a large population, facilitating an in-depth understanding of the problem under investigation (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

Population of the Study

The study's target population comprised women engaged in agricultural activities and in governance-related institutions in Nigeria. This includes female farmers, agricultural extension officers, policymakers in the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, and representatives from women's agricultural associations and cooperatives. These groups were selected because they are directly affected by socio-cultural norms and institutional policies that shape women's participation in agricultural governance.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A sample of 275 respondents was selected from the target population using a combination of stratified and simple random sampling. Stratification by geopolitical zones ensured fair representation across Nigeria, and random sampling was used to select participants within each stratum. This approach minimises bias and ensures that the sample adequately represents the diverse experiences of women across regions and institutional levels (Etikan & Bala, 2017).

Instrument for Data Collection

The primary data were collected through a structured questionnaire and semi-structured interviews. The questionnaire consisted of both closed-ended and open-ended questions designed to elicit responses on socio-cultural and institutional factors influencing women's participation in agricultural governance. The semi-structured interviews were conducted with key informants, including senior officers in agricultural ministries, leaders of women's cooperatives, and agricultural policymakers, providing deeper insights into institutional practices and challenges (Kothari, 2014).

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

To ensure content validity, the research instrument was reviewed by experts in agricultural economics and gender studies who provided suggestions for improvement. A pilot test was conducted with 30 respondents from a similar population outside the study area, and the instrument's reliability was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding a coefficient of 0.82, indicating high internal consistency (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011).

Method of Data Collection

Data collection was conducted through direct administration of the questionnaires to respondents, with the assistance of trained research assistants. Interviews were also conducted in person and recorded with participants' consent. Ethical considerations, including confidentiality, informed consent, and voluntary participation, were strictly adhered to throughout the process.

Method of Data Analysis

Data obtained from the questionnaires were coded and analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, and mean scores were used to summarise the data. In contrast, inferential statistics, including multiple regression analysis, were employed to examine the relationship between socio-cultural and institutional constraints and women’s involvement in agricultural governance. Qualitative data from interviews were analysed thematically to complement the quantitative findings (Braun & Clarke, 2019).

Data Presentation and Analysis of Results

Socio-Demographic and Economic Characteristics of the Respondents

The demographic characteristics of respondents provide an important foundation for understanding the socio-cultural and institutional barriers influencing women’s participation in national agricultural governance in Nigeria. Data were obtained from women stakeholders, including policymakers, farmers, NGO representatives, and agricultural extension officers, across the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) in Abuja.

Table 1: Sex of Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	96	34.9
Female	179	65.1
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

Table 1 shows the gender composition of the respondents. Females accounted for 65.1% of participants, while males accounted for 34.9%. This high female representation indicates that the study successfully captured women’s perspectives within the agricultural governance space. It also reflects the growing interest of women in agricultural policy and leadership discussions, reinforcing the relevance of this study in exploring the constraints affecting their active participation.

Table 2: Age of Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18–25	71	31.3
26–35	108	47.6
36–45	51	22.5
46–55	42	18.5
56 and above	3	1.3
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

Table 2 shows that the largest age group among respondents is 26-35 years (47.6%), followed by 18–25 years (31.3%). The smallest group comprises respondents aged 56 and above (1.3%). This youthful dominance indicates an active generation of women increasingly engaged in agricultural

leadership and advocacy roles. Younger women are vital drivers of innovation and gender reform in the agricultural sector, and their involvement bodes well for the future of inclusive governance.

Table 3: Marital Status of Respondents

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	137	49.8
Married	130	47.3
Divorced	1	0.4
Widowed	7	2.5
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

Table 3 presents the marital distribution of respondents. Single women (49.8%) and married women (47.3%) make up the majority, while divorced and widowed women constitute only 2.9%. This nearly balanced ratio shows that women across various marital statuses engage in agricultural governance. However, cultural expectations tied to marital status can influence the level of autonomy women have in contributing to decision-making, highlighting a socio-cultural factor that needs to be addressed through inclusive policies.

Table 4: Educational Level of Respondents

Educational Level	Frequency	Percentage
No Formal Education	0	0.0
Primary	1	0.4
Secondary	24	8.7
Tertiary	250	90.9
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

As shown in Table 4, the majority of respondents (90.9%) have attained tertiary education, while only 8.7% have secondary education and 0.4% primary education. This high literacy level suggests that most of the women involved are well-positioned to participate in policy formulation and advocacy. Education enhances women’s understanding of agricultural systems, increases confidence in leadership, and empowers them to navigate institutional frameworks effectively.

Table 5: Occupation of Respondents

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Policy Makers	108	39.3
Farmers Organisation Officers	46	16.7
Extension Workers	20	7.3
NGO Representatives (e.g., NWAP-DI)	22	8.0
Farmers	66	24.0
Students	10	3.6
Others	3	1.1
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

Table 5 presents the occupational distribution of respondents. The largest group (39.3%) are policymakers, followed by farmers (24.0%) and farmers’ organisation officers (16.7%). The inclusion of extension workers and NGO representatives reflects a multi-sectoral representation of the agricultural landscape. This diversity strengthens the study’s analysis by capturing perspectives from both institutional and grassroots levels of governance.

Table 6: Length of Experience in Agriculture

Experience (Years)	Frequency	Percentage
0–5	134	49.1
6–10	61	22.3
11–15	38	13.9
16 and above	42	15.3
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

Table 6 shows that nearly half of the respondents (49.1%) have 0-5 years of experience in agriculture, while 15.3% have more than 16 years. This blend of new entrants and seasoned professionals suggests intergenerational engagement in agricultural governance. The presence of experienced women provides valuable institutional memory, while the growing number of new entrants indicates increased awareness and empowerment initiatives promoting gender participation.

Women’s Participation in Agricultural Governance

Table 7: Awareness of Federal Ministries Involved in Agricultural Governance

Awareness	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	209	76.0
No	66	24.0
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

Table 7 shows that 76% of respondents are aware of federal ministries involved in agricultural governance. This demonstrates increased policy visibility but also implies that awareness is not yet universal. Ensuring equitable access to information across rural and urban areas would help bridge awareness gaps.

Table 8: Adequacy of Women’s Involvement in Agricultural Governance

Involvement	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	138	50.2
No	82	29.8
Not Sure	55	20.0
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

Half of the respondents (50.2%) believe women are adequately involved in governance, while 29.8% disagree. This mixed view suggests uneven representation across different administrative levels. Institutional reforms and inclusion policies are needed to deepen participation.

Table 9: Active Participation of Women in Decision-Making

Participation	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	204	74.5
No	44	16.1
Not Sure	27	9.8
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The data in Table 9 show that 74.5% of respondents confirmed that women actively participate in agricultural decision-making. This suggests notable progress in gender inclusion, likely resulting from advocacy, training, and policy support programs.

Challenges Affecting Women’s Participation

Table 16: Obstacles Preventing Women’s Participation

Obstacles	Frequency	Percentage
Socio-Cultural Norms	133	48.4
Limited Access to Resources	38	13.8
Lack of Education or Skills	38	13.8
Underrepresentation in Leadership Roles	66	24.0
Total	275	100

Source: Field Survey, April 2025

The results indicate that socio-cultural norms (48.4%) are the most significant barrier, followed by underrepresentation in leadership (24.0%). These findings affirm that cultural expectations and institutional biases still hinder gender equity in agricultural governance.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study demonstrate that women in Nigeria’s agricultural governance systems are increasingly aware of, and engaged in, decision-making processes at both institutional and grassroots levels. Approximately three-quarters of respondents indicated active participation in agricultural governance, reflecting the impact of awareness campaigns, training programs, and institutional support designed to enhance women’s visibility in the sector. This level of engagement suggests that women are not only contributing to policy discussions but are also shaping practical agricultural interventions that affect both food production and rural livelihoods. The growing presence of women in policymaking spaces underscores their potential to influence governance structures and ensure that agricultural programs and policies are more responsive to the needs of female farmers and communities.

Despite this progress, the study highlights persistent challenges that limit women's full participation and influence in agricultural governance. Socio-cultural norms remain a significant barrier, as nearly half of the respondents identified traditional gender expectations and societal roles as obstacles to engagement. Additionally, underrepresentation in leadership positions constrains women's decision-making authority, reducing their capacity to advocate effectively for gender-sensitive policies. Even when programs and policies exist, such as the National Gender Policy and the National Agricultural Transformation Implementation Policy (NATIP), inconsistent implementation and limited dissemination undermine their effectiveness at the community level. These structural and cultural constraints illustrate that awareness and participation alone are insufficient to achieve meaningful gender equity without systemic reforms.

The findings further emphasise the need for multifaceted strategies to enhance women's inclusion in agricultural governance. Strengthening institutional mechanisms, providing targeted capacity-building opportunities, and ensuring consistent enforcement of gender-inclusive policies are critical steps toward creating an enabling environment for women. Moreover, cultural reorientation efforts, including community sensitisation and advocacy campaigns, are necessary to address deeply rooted social norms that restrict women's agency. By combining policy, institutional, and socio-cultural interventions, Nigeria can move closer to fully integrating women into agricultural decision-making processes, thereby promoting equitable governance, sustainable agricultural development, and long-term food security.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study concludes that while women in Nigeria's agricultural governance systems are increasingly aware of and engaged in decision-making processes, significant socio-cultural and institutional barriers continue to limit their full participation and influence. Findings indicate that although gender-inclusive policies, such as the National Gender Policy and the National Agricultural Transformation Implementation Policy (NATIP), exist, their implementation remains inconsistent, and many women remain underrepresented in leadership roles. Socio-cultural norms, limited access to resources, and insufficient capacity-building initiatives further constrain women's ability to contribute effectively to agricultural governance. Nevertheless, the active involvement of women in both federal institutions and grassroots organisations demonstrates their potential to shape policies, advocate for equitable resource allocation, and enhance agricultural productivity. Achieving full gender equity in agricultural decision-making requires addressing structural, cultural, and institutional challenges simultaneously.

Based on the findings, it is recommended that policymakers and relevant stakeholders implement targeted capacity-building programs to equip women with skills and knowledge for leadership roles in agriculture. Institutional mechanisms should be strengthened to ensure consistent enforcement of gender-inclusive policies, while awareness campaigns and community sensitisation efforts should address restrictive socio-cultural norms. Additionally, federal ministries and women's organisations should foster inclusive platforms for dialogue, mentorship, and policy advocacy to increase women's representation in decision-making. These interventions will enhance women's participation, promote equitable governance, and contribute to sustainable agricultural development in Nigeria.

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